

Software Management Plan – Version V1.2.0

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Versioning

Version	Date	Authors (/feedback implemented by)	Feedback provided by	Notes
1.0	27.01.2026	Stijn de Laat, Linus Band, Leonie Dudda	/	First SMP version
1.0.1	02.02.3026		Lilit Dulyan	
1.1	26.03.2026	Leonie Dudda, Stijn de Laat, Linus Band		We added/changed questions to adhere to the NWO/ZonMw RDM Requirements. We implemented the feedback
1.1.1	10.04.2026		Miriam Kos, Pauline Roost	
1.2	14.04.2026	Leonie Dudda, Stijn de Laat, Linus Band		We implemented the feedback
	11.06.2026		Approved in a feedback session with data stewards and researchers	

Legend

_____ open text field

[[]] selection of multiple answers possible

[] selection of one of the answers

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1. General information

1.1 Title of this SMP

Info: For example: R software package for the analysis of between-subject IAT data

1.2 Summary of research proposal

Info: Please write a brief summary of the project that involves research software

1.3 University, faculty, institute, department

Info: Please fill in at which University, faculty, institute, and department the research project is going to be conducted. In case of multiple universities, faculties, institutes or departments, please specify all.

University: _____

Faculty: _____

Institute (if applicable): _____

Department: _____

1.4 What are the project number, funder and funder ID?

Project number: _____

Funder: _____

Funder ID: _____

Not applicable

1.5 What is the (expected) start and end date of the project?

Info: For the start date, please indicate the approximate point at which you expect to start programming your software. For the end date, please indicate the approximate point at which you expect the software to be ready for release.

Start date: _____

End date: _____

1.6 Which researcher(s) and/or relevant parties are involved in the research project, and what are their roles regarding software development and management?

Info: Involved parties may include student assistants, PhD supervisors, (departmental) software developers, and other third parties, like hosting services, consortium partners, legal consultants, etc.

Researcher(s) and/or relevant parties...

Involved in developing the software/code:

Involved in storage and backup during the project:

Involved in long term archiving and sharing after the project, including transfer of management roles and (long-term) maintenance:

Involved in writing and updating the SMP

1.7 Who is the rights holder of the software that you will create during the project?

Info: If applicable, please check your funding agreement for any clauses that specify ownership or usage rights for the research outputs. If you need further support, you can consult legal affairs. The default is that Radboud University is the rights holder.

Radboud University is the rights holder of my research software.

My research is funded and the agreement states that the rights holder of the research software is my funder, namely: _____

Other, namely: _____

1.8 Do you need to create or sign any agreements during the project (such as consortium agreements and non-disclosure agreements)? If yes, please specify the agreements.

Info: For instance, non-disclosure agreements can impose restrictions that may influence whether, when, or how your software can be published.

No such agreements are required for my research.

Yes, the following agreements are required for my research. Please specify and, if possible, attach the agreement to the SMP: _____

1.9 Do you need approval from an ethics committee for your project? Please explain why (not).

1.10 Did you consult a local expert (e.g., your institute's software- or data steward/trainer) when writing this SMP?

Yes

Date(s) of the consultation(s): _____

Name(s) of the expert(s): _____

No

2. Software specifics

2.1 Will you (partly) use existing software?

Info: Also include software packages or other dependencies.

I will not use any existing software.

I will use existing software, namely: _____

○ What are the terms of reuse? _____

2.2 What is the type of the software that is developed in the project?

Info: If applicable, you can select multiple answers.

Analysis script

Computational model

Pre-processing pipeline

Data gathering

REST service

Driver

Other, namely: _____

2.3 What is the intended goal(s) of the software that is developed in the project?

Info: For example, analysis of medical images, statistical analysis of behavioural data, software packages for a user community, etc.

2.4 What is the software's intended user community?

Info: Please specify the (group of) people or organizations who are expected to use the software.

2.5 What programming language(s) do you intend to use?

Info: Please note that open-source languages (e.g., Python, R) are encouraged, but proprietary ones might still be favoured in your specific field.

I will use [LANGUAGE] for [SPECIFY PART OF SOFTWARE IF APPLICABLE].

2.6 What programming environment(s) do you intend to use?

Info: For example: PyCharm, RStudio, Notepad++.

I will use [ENVIRONMENT] for [SPECIFY PART OF SOFTWARE IF APPLICABLE].

3. Data

3.1 Do you use data?

Info: You can select multiple options.

No

Yes, simulated data (for testing)

Yes, existing real data from this source: _____

- What are the terms of reuse? _____

Yes, I will collect my own data, namely: _____

- Please consult a software trainer or steward. They can advise you on whether a Data Management Plan is also required. Provide a brief description of the data here:

4. Version management and storage

4.1 What devices do you use to develop and/or run your software?

Info: You can select multiple options

Radboud work laptop

HPC, namely: _____

Private pc/laptop

Other, namely: _____

4.2 What kind of version control do you intend to use?

Info: It is recommended to use version control from the start to track different versions in your local repository. You can select multiple options.

Git

Mercurial

SVN

Other, namely: _____

4.3 What kind of versioning scheme to you intend to use?

Semantic versioning, e.g. 0.9.2 or 12.1.0

Calendar versioning, e.g. v2025-12-22

Other, namely: _____

4.4 Do you intend to use an external repository?

Info: Version control is generally used in tandem with an online repository, which provides an external backup, as well as a place to make your software publicly available.

Yes, namely (multiple choices possible):

Codeberg

GitLab

GitHub

Bitbucket

Other, namely: _____

No, because: [Please explain your reasoning] _____

5. Reusability

5.1 What quality control will you use?

Tests, namely: [PLEASE SPECIFY THE TYPE OF TEST: FOR EXAMPLE, UNIT, FUNCTIONAL, INTEGRATION, LINTING, REGRESSION]

The code will be checked by: [PLEASE SPECIFY: FOR EXAMPLE, SOFTWARE DEVELOPER, STATISTICIAN, RESEARCH SOFTWARE ENGINEER, ETC.]

Other, namely: _____

None, because: _____

5.2 How will you document what the software does and how it should be used (including system requirements)?

Info: For example, you could include a README file and/or explain the code directly within the script. The purpose of the documentation is to make the code understandable for both regular users and your future self.

5.3 How will you ensure that others can contribute to the software?

Info: This can vary from inline documentation (like comments or docstrings) to codes of conduct or contributing guidelines, to architectural diagrams showing the structure of the program. Please focus on contributors.

5.4 Are there any (other) external factors that users and developers should be mindful of when interacting with your software?

Info: This could include hardware requirements, licensing constraints, etc.

6. Long-term archiving and maintenance

6.1 Where will you archive (versions of) your software for the long term?

Info: This refers to where you will store long-term, archived versions of your software in addition to the version-control systems you use during development. Keep in mind that platforms like GitHub do not provide guaranteed long-term preservation.

- RDR [I will archive the following versions or parts of my software in the RDR [PLEASE EXPLAIN WHICH VERSIONS/PARTS OF THE SOFTWARE]. The software will be accompanied by a unique and persistent identifier by default.]
- Zenodo [I will archive the following versions or parts of my software in the RDR [PLEASE EXPLAIN WHICH VERSIONS/PARTS OF THE SOFTWARE]. I will make sure that the software will be accompanied by a unique and persistent identifier.]
- SoftwareHeritage.org [I will archive the following versions or parts of my software in the RDR [PLEASE EXPLAIN WHICH VERSIONS/PARTS OF THE SOFTWARE]. I will make sure that the software will be accompanied by a unique and persistent identifier.]
- Other, namely: _____ [PLEASE FILL IN WHICH REPOSITORY YOU ARE GOING TO USE]. I will archive the following versions or parts of my software in the [NAME REPOSITORY] [PLEASE EXPLAIN WHICH VERSIONS/PARTS OF THE SOFTWARE]. I will make sure that the software will be accompanied by a unique and persistent identifier.]]

6.2 How and when will your software be distributed/published for reuse?

Info: For example, you could make the software accessible to others through a public code repository, a research software archive, a package manager, a project website, or a publication. In most cases, this will happen after completion of the software or after publication.

- I will distribute my software for reuse through: _____
- I will not distribute it for reuse. Please explain your reasoning: _____

6.3 Under what access level and licence will you publish (parts of) your software?

Info: Please note that it should be compatible with the licences of used dependencies and libraries. Note that the RU has a [decision tree](#) for deciding on a licence. For checking compatibility, you may also consult this [compatibility matrix](#). If you are only going to publish parts of your software, please specify which parts.

- I will publish my software.
- Access level:
- Open access
- Restricted access, because: [Please explain your reasoning and who will have access]
- _____
- Licence: _____
- I will not publish my software, because: [Please explain your reasoning] _____

6.4 What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organised?

Info: This could, for example, include a dedicated contact person, office hours, trainings/workshops, or an issue tracking system.

- I will provide the following support: _____
- I will not provide any support, because: [Please explain your reasoning] _____

6.5 How will you procure long-term maintenance for your software?

Info: Long-term maintenance ensures that the software remains usable, secure, and reliable for future users and for any research that depends on it. This maintenance could include securing funding, assigning responsibility to a team or steward, arranging community-based maintenance, or planning periodic updates.

- Yes, through: _____
- I do not plan to procure long-term maintenance, because: [Please explain your reasoning]
- _____

6.6 What is your software retirement strategy?

Info: At some point you may decide to stop maintaining your software. Consider whether you will remove it from package managers, whether it will remain available but no longer be updated, and how you will communicate this to users and external parties. Also think about whether any associated databases need to be shut down. Note that the software should not be removed from its repository.
